

COGNITION AND SPEECH DEVELOPMENT IN CHILDREN

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***Abstract.** This article is concerned with the development of speech and cognition in children as well as the correlation between speech and cognition . It also deals with we can be done to help children with a delay in cognitive development.*

***Key words:** Speech, communication, cognition, cognitive development, speech delay, correlation.*

Introduction. In linguistics, speech is defined as a communication tool utilizing spoken words or in some cases sound symbols. Interaction between language and cognition remains an unsolved scientific problem. What are the differences in neural mechanisms of language and cognition? Why do children acquire language by the age of six, while taking a lifetime to acquire cognition? There is not a lot of discussion on connection between speech and cognition. Some argue that it impacts it, while others disagree.

Main part. The importance of cognition cannot be overestimated. Some reasons as to why cognition is important are as follows: we are affected by cognition in different areas of life such as relationships, work , studies ; people's need for cognition to acquire a new concept ; Cognition not only affects things inside kids' heads but outside as well. Their attention, memory, problem-solving, and judgments contribute to how they behave and interact with the environment.

People tend to think that cognition develops later in life or as children grow up. Cognition starts developing as soon as the baby is born. The very first signs of

cognitive development are, understanding what objects are and how they work. That is an object exists even if it is out of sight. In children and toddlers, cognition develops through senses such as touch, feel, and everyday sensory-motor experiences. They understand cause and effect. Imitation is also seen as a cognitive skill. A simple skill such as following an object or turning pages is a cognitive skill. As they grow older, understanding how things fit in space, figuring out how a toy works are some other cognitive skills that develop. Even developing language is a cognitive skill such as understanding and expressing words [2].

Correlation between speech and cognition is the most debated topic. What is the relationship between cognition and speech and language development? Both are interrelated. One cannot function or develop without the other. Children require cognitive skills such as attention to grasp the sounds made by the mother. They need to process and store these in their long and short-term memory for further use. They need to differentiate between sounds. Build vocabulary and form patterns. This pattern-building skill will help kids to learn the grammar of the language. Understanding the sentence structure, pattern of sentences, etc. In later stages, cognitive skills such as problem-solving, feelings, understanding body language, decision making will help them build relationships with peers. It will also help them during play. Reasoning and logic will help kids to understand academic as well as everyday aspects. Cognition is also dependent on language. For instance: if language isn't developing typically, but cognition is solid. Children cannot express reasoning. The means of expressing cognition is through language. Until the age of 3 years, it is complicated to tell cognition and language apart [3].

Impact of cognition on speech. What results in the delay of understanding is the delay of cognitive skills, meaning that prepositions, directions and adjectives do not make sense to children, which in turn leads to a delay in talking. With such problems, academic difficulties occur. Overall development is influenced by cognition. How can we be of assistance to children with related problems? It is often argued that playing and interacting with children can help foster language

skills and cognition. They are as follows: Let your baby explore toys and move; Singing and reading; Answering why questions; Talking to them; Provide them with choices and help them make thoughtful decisions.

Conclusion. Overall development is influenced by cognition. How can we be of assistance to children with related problems? It is often argued that playing and interacting with children can help foster language skills and cognition. They are as follows: Let your baby explore toys and move; Singing and reading; Answering why questions; Talking to them; Provide them with choices and help them make thoughtful decisions. [4]

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